

Determination of Mechanical Properties of Polyimide - Silica Nanocomposite Using Micromechanical Modeling

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- The demand for high-speed electronics is rapidly increasing, leading to more demanding printed wiring board (PWB) requirements.
 - 5G Communication Devices
 - Solid-State Drives (SSDs)
 - Microprocessors etc.
- A typical PWB is made by bonding dielectric films like polyimide to electrically conductive copper foil, such as rolled annealed (RA) copper.
- PWBs are expected to become thinner, more flexible, durable, and compatible with high-frequency 5G performance.
- Polyimide films naturally have a higher coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) than copper foils, which results in a mismatch and causes residual thermal stresses.

To reduce the CTE mismatch, silica nanoparticles can be added to the polyimide films to lower their CTE.

The focus of this work is to understand crack propagation in the PI-Silica substrate

90° Peel Test – Current Configuration

Force – displacement curve

Plastic deformation of copper after the peel test

- The force-displacement curve obtained from the peel test does not accurately represent the adhesion properties of Cu-PI.
- To capture the adhesion properties of Cu-PI, it is necessary to separate all other deformation energies from the materials, such as the plastic deformation of copper.

Crack Propagate Through PI Film (XPS Experiment)

Surface of Cu side and PI side after peel test

- XPS (X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy) was used to analyze each side of the failure interface.
- The surface analysis reveals that crack interpenetration is occurring within the PI film.
 - PI material is present on both sides of the crack surface.
 - This indicates that the crack does not propagate along the PI–Cu interface, but rather through the bulk of the PI film.
 - Further investigation is needed to understand the role of embedded particles within the PI.

› Establishing RVE

- Residual stress (polyimide/silica)
- Inelastic properties of polyimide
- Traction law (polyimide/silica) (from MD modeling)
- Predict the effective properties
 - Relate to particle debonding/cracking

- Copper bulk properties
- Traction law (copper/surface of polymer (MD modeling))

Failure mode could be at the interface or cracking through the polyimide depending on level of adhesion

- Embedded cell modeling approach (Canal et al., CST 2012) – embed fiber-matrix microstructure into continuum
- Assembled microstructure from randomly selected unit cells from 17 realizations (MATLAB)
- This ensured 60% FVF, no fibers touching (causes very small finite elements, drives down timestep)

60% FVF Unit Cell

16 DOF

Polyimide (PI)

Silica Nanoparticle (SNP)

Single particle composite (cut section for better view)

$$V_s = \frac{4}{3}\pi R^3$$

$$V_r = L^3$$

$$V_p = \frac{V_s}{V_r}$$

Mechanical properties

Maximum V_p when $L = 2R$; $V_p = \frac{\pi}{6} = 0.52$

	Modulus (GPa)	Yield stress (MPa)	Poisson's Ratio	CTE (ppm/°C)
Polyimide (PI)	3.81 ± 0.05	76 ± 1	0.34	20
Silica	73		0.17	0.52

- Volume fraction $V_p = 5.7, 12$ and 26.5%

- Einstein's equation
 - Based on the rigid particle assumption

$$\frac{E_c}{E_m} = 1 + 2.5V_p$$

- Guth's equation
 - Added a particle interaction term in the Einstein equation

$$\frac{E_c}{E_m} = 1 + 2.5V_p + 14.1V_p^2$$

- Halpin and Tsai's equation
 - Semi-empirical relationship

$$\frac{E_c}{E_m} = \frac{1 + A_1 B_1 V_p}{1 - B_1 V_p} \quad B_1 = \frac{\frac{E_p}{E_m} - 1}{\frac{E_p}{E_m} + A_1}$$

- $A_1 = 1$

- Assumption of theoretical model

- Perfect bonding between interface
- No residual stress
- Both fiber and matrix are elastic

- Kerner's equation

- $E_p \gg E_m$

$$\frac{E_c}{E_m} = 1 + \frac{V_p}{(1 - V_p)} \frac{15(1 - \nu_m)}{(8 - 10\nu_m)}$$

- Mooney's equation

$$\frac{E_c}{E_m} = \exp\left(\frac{2.5V_p}{1 - sV_p}\right)$$

- $s = 1.43$

- Lower bound

$$E_c^{lower} = E_p E_m / [E_p(1 - V_p) + E_m V_p]$$

- Upper bound

$$E_c^{upper} = [E_p V_p + E_m(1 - V_p)]$$

Effective Modulus at Different V_p

- Experimental comparison is needed to determine the best fit for the model.

Comparison of CTE with Theoretical Model

- Results from various analytical models are compared with the proposed FE model.
- Kerner's model shows strong correlation with the FE model.
- The bounds for the CTE of copper is 16 - 18 ppm/°C
- PI (polyimide) CTE values considered: 20 ppm/°C (room temperature) and 40 ppm/°C (higher temperature).
- The required silica V_p is determined to be approximately 0.125 at room temperature and 0.5 at the higher service temperature range.

Boundary Conditions for FE Model

Constant Displacement (CD) BC

$$\epsilon_y = \frac{\Delta v}{L} \quad \epsilon_z = \frac{\Delta w}{W}$$

$$\nu = -\frac{\epsilon_z}{\epsilon_y} \quad E = \frac{\sigma_y}{\epsilon_y}$$

$$\sigma_y = \frac{\text{average force}}{\text{area}}$$

Constant Pressure (CP) BC

$$\epsilon_y = \frac{\Delta v}{L} \quad \epsilon_z = \frac{\Delta w}{W}$$

$$\nu = -\frac{\epsilon_z}{\epsilon_y} \quad E = \frac{\sigma_y}{\epsilon_y}$$

$\Delta v = \text{Average displacement}$

Tensile loading in y direction

- The 3D generalized plane strain boundary condition is not straight forward in Abaqus
- Plane surface should be plane
 - Edges are shared with two planes
 - Vertices are shared between three planes
- “Equation” option in Abaqus is suitable for applying multiple DOF constraints
- Both the resin and particles are modeled using three-dimensional eight-node elements (C3D8).
- For the elastic analysis, a converged mesh size of 2 nm was obtained.

Tensile loading in y direction

Effective CTE and Modulus Calculation

In put

	Modulus (GPa)	Yield stress (MPa)	Poisson's Ratio	CTE (ppm/°C)
Polyimide (PI)	3.81 ± 0.05	76 ± 1	0.34	20
Silica	73		0.17	0.52

Effective CTE - Simulation result

V_p (%)	5.7	12	26.5
CTE (ppm/°C)	18.3	16.8	13.8

Elastic modulus – simulation result and validation

V_p (W_p) (%)	5.7 (10)	12 (20)	26.5 (40)
Experiment (MPa)	4407 ± 96	4948 ± 159	6417 ± 102
FE model - CD (MPa)	4280	4898	7748
FE model - CP (MPa)	4197	4618	5908

- Strains in all three directions are equal

$$CTE = \frac{\epsilon_x}{\Delta T} = \frac{\epsilon_y}{\Delta T} = \frac{\epsilon_z}{\Delta T}$$

$$\epsilon_y = \frac{\Delta v}{L}$$

- › Stress-strain curve of PI is fitted to a Ramberg-Osgood equation in terms of strain:

$$\sigma = \frac{E\varepsilon}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{E\varepsilon}{\sigma_0}\right)^a\right)^{\frac{1}{a}}}$$

$$a = 2.7$$

$$\sigma_0 = 138 \text{ MPa}$$

$$E = 1.4 \text{ GPa}$$

- In Abaqus, the resin is modeled as linear elastic up to the yield stress, and the nonlinear behavior is defined using the tabular input method.
- Resin failure is modeled as ductile damage using a strain-based failure criterion.

Property of copper considering the processing conditions

Property of PI – Silica films at different silica weight fraction

Mesh Convergence Study – Constant Displacement ($V_p = 26.5\%$)

- Mesh convergence studies were conducted with different sizes ranging from 4 nm to 0.5 nm.
- Both global and local properties were studied.
- It was observed from the plot that, after a mesh size of 2 nm, both elastic and plastic solutions converged within a 5% error.

Stress – Strain Curves at Different V_p

- Inputting the stress – strain curve of PI and changing the V_p
- Comparing FE results with experiment
- **With out considering thermal loading**

Constant Displacement (CD)
Constant Pressure (CP)
Frictionless (FL)

- At lower V_p , FE results has good correlation with experiments
- At $V_p = 26.5\%$ experimental stress – strain curve is close to the FE model with constant pressure BC
- Perfect bonding is the upper bond and FL is the lower bond.
 - **Need to include residual stress, frictional sliding and include traction law to predict debonding between interface**

Mesh Convergence Studies with Damage (CD)

- Inputting the stress – strain curve of PI and strain to failure from experiment (~15%)
- $V_p = 26.5\%$
- Perfect bonding between PI and Silica interface
- With out considering thermal loading
- Both failure stress and energy (area under the stress – strain curve) are very sensitive to mesh
- It is observed from the plot, after mesh size of 1 nm both failure stress and energy are converged with in the 5% error

mesh size = 1 nm

Plastic strain to failure from experiment =
~0.13 and ~0.10

- Inputting the stress – strain curve of PI and varying strain to failure (15% to 12%)
- $V_p = 26.5\%$
- Perfect bonding between PI and Silica interface
- With out considering thermal loading
- Damage initiation/propagation may change if we consider other damage mechanisms in the model

Considering Three Particles RVE (CD)

mesh size = 1 nm

$\epsilon_y = \sim 0.035$

$\epsilon_y = \sim 0.038$

- Considering three particles in the RVE as the first step of building cell model
- Inputting the stress – strain curve of PI and strain to failure from experiment (~15%)
- $V_p = 26.5\%$
- **Perfect bonding between PI and Silica interface**
- **With out considering thermal loading**
- **Only middle region has failure criteria**

Considering Three Particles RVE (CP)

mesh size = 1 nm

Applied pressure
= ~135 MPa

Applied pressure
= ~140 MPa

- Considering three particles in the RVE as the first step of building cell model
- Inputting the stress – strain curve of PI and strain to failure from experiment (~15%)
- $V_p = 26.5\%$
- Perfect bonding between PI and Silica interface
- With out considering thermal loading
- Only middle region has failure criteria

- Single RVE study has completed and compared with experiment.
- Including CTE and different damage mechanisms study the RVE at different loading conditions and volume fractions.
- Develop the cell model by inputting the properties of the constituents and stacking the RVE with a random distribution.
 - Residual stress
 - Resin Plasticity
 - Frictional sliding and interface debonding
- Next, measure the peel strength of copper/polyimide laminates to understand the underlying mechanism.

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